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Foreign investment and the development of the stock market in Spain (1961-2007)

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ABSTRACT

This article reconstructs the dynamics of foreign investment in the Spanish stock market between 1961 and 2007, exploring a less explored dimension of financial globalisation and market modernisation in Spain. By building a novel database, it analyses investment trends by sectors, companies, countries of origin, and types of investors, offering a detailed view of the evolution of foreign capital during Spain's reintegration into the global economy. The results highlight the concentration of foreign investment in banking and energy, its increasing focus on a small number of companies, and the key role of economic partners such as the United Kingdom. By tracing the phases of the stock market's internationalisation, the paper reveals the significant presence of foreign capital in the 1960s and its resurgence following European integration.

KEYWORDS: Foreign investment, stock market, globalisation, Spain

JEL CODES: N24, F21, G15, G11

1. Introduction

Foreign investment is a key component of modern stock markets. In the case of Spain, its presence has dominated trading activity and played a crucial role in the opening and modernisation of the secondary market since the last third of the 20th century. Key events such as the country's accession to the European Economic Community (EEC) in 1986, the securities market reform of 1988, the signing of the Maastricht Treaty in 1992, and the adoption of the euro in 1999 deepened Spain's international integration, marking the end of a previous period characterised by limited foreign capital involvement (Moreno Castaño 2006). As a result, foreign investment in the Spanish stock exchange grew from

just 2.5% of total traded capital in 1976 to over 50% by the end of the century, surpassing the activity of domestic investors.

The presence of foreign capital in Spain has received significant attention in historiography. Indeed, works such as those by Tascón Fernández (2008), Bajo-Rubio (2021), Puig and Álvaro-Moya (2018; 2016), and Puig and Castro (2009), among many others, have analysed the arrival of foreign flows since the mid-19th century and highlighted the impact of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the Spanish economy and its companies, as well as its role as a driver of economic growth, productivity, and the transfer of technology and knowledge. This academic literature has focused on the arrival of foreign investment in general but has not examined the specific channel through which it occurs. Indeed, foreign investment can take the form of either FDI or portfolio investment. Existing studies have largely focused on the former, paying little attention to the latter as well as the role of the stock market as a conduit for FDI and its impact on the modernisation and internationalisation of the Spanish economy.¹ This paper addresses that key gap by offering a quantitative long-term perspective on the presence of foreign capital in the Spanish stock market from 1961 to 2007. This approach allows us to shed new light on the under-researched years of the Franco regime and spans a crucial period in which Spain reintegrated into the global economy and emerged as a key player in Europe.

The contribution of this paper is multifaceted. On the one hand, we build a novel and comprehensive database that, for the first time, quantitatively reconstructs the annual evolution of foreign investment in the Spanish stock exchange. This dataset allows for a detailed analysis by sector (1961-2007), company (1989-2007), country of origin (1984-2007), and type of investor (1991-2007). The sectoral analysis shows how foreign activity has concentrated in banking and energy as traditional destinations, while other sectors evolved in line with the Spanish business cycle. Furthermore, trading has become increasingly concentrated in a smaller number of companies, which already attracted significant attention from domestic investors. The geographical analysis of the source of funds reveals the importance of Spain's traditional economic partners, with the United Kingdom standing out as a major financial intermediary and conduit for institutional investment flows from other parts of the world.

On the other hand, we provide a novel and systematic account of the role played by foreign capital inflows in the globalisation, opening, and growth of Spanish stock markets. In particular, the compilation of time series has allowed us to outline the main stages in the internationalisation of the Spanish stock exchange and uncover the unique importance of foreign capital in the secondary market after the opening marked by the 1959 Stabilisation Plan, as well as its sharp decline in the late 1960s. This suggests that

¹ Portfolio investment focuses on acquiring financial assets without achieving direct influence over the issuing entities. FDI, on the contrary, is defined as ownership stakes exceeding 10% of a company's share capital (International Monetary Fund 2013).

foreign investment in the stock market did not evolve in parallel with FDI, which continued growing in those years.

The paper is organised into six sections. The first provides a historiographical review of studies on foreign investment in Spain. The second section presents the data used, which primarily come from the investment statistics of non-residents from the Madrid Stock Exchange and the Ministry of Economy and Trade. The third section examines, in line with Spain's economic history, the general evolution of foreign investment flows. The fourth and fifth sections analyse, respectively, the sectors and companies receiving investment and the countries and types of investors providing those funds. The final section presents the main conclusions.

2. Foreign capital in Spain

In Spain's contemporary history, foreign capital has played an essential role in the development of key economic sectors, ranging from industry and energy to financial services (Tortella 1995). Its influence has been particularly significant since the mid-20th century, a period defined by increasing international economic integration and domestic reforms that facilitated the arrival of foreign investors (Puig and Álvaro-Moya 2015; Tascón Fernández 2008).

Numerous studies have analysed FDI in Spain, examining its impact on both economic growth and corporate structures. According to Bajo-Rubio (2021), the inflow of FDI enabled Spain to accelerate its integration into the global economy while fostering significant improvements in technology transfer and the creation of high-quality employment. Thus, it served as a driver of long-term economic growth and productivity, particularly in the manufacturing sector (Cebrián 2001). On the other hand, the uneven spatial distribution of investment contributed to economic divergence between regions. Bajo-Rubio et al. (2007) argue that the regions receiving the highest FDI inflows after Spain joined the EEC were those that experienced the greatest growth. However, Myro (2015) reverses the causality, suggesting that the more developed regions with better infrastructure attracted higher levels of capital.

Other authors highlight how the expansion of foreign multinationals in Spain has had a positive impact on market efficiency and the competitiveness of local firms, driven by the transfer of technical knowledge and the adoption of new management practices (Cebrián 2005; García-Canal et al. 2018; Guillén 2005; Guillén and García-Canal 2010; Puig and Álvaro-Moya 2018; 2016; Puig and Castro 2009). These companies acted as catalysts for the structural transformation of the Spanish economy, beginning in the early 1950s and particularly following the 1959 Stabilisation Plan and the country's entry into the EEC in 1986. Some of these studies emphasise the importance of specific countries in driving foreign investment inflows to Spain, such as the United States (Álvaro-Moya 2012; 2011; Puig 2002), France (Castro 2010; Castro and Sánchez 2015; Sánchez 2006), and Germany (San Román, Puig, and Gil-López 2023).

On the contrary, since the 1980s, portfolio investment has accounted for most of the foreign capital flows to Spain, primarily channelled through the stock market. However, this form of investment has received significantly less attention in the academic literature. This scarcity contrasts with the stock market's importance as a driver of business activity and a key mechanism for attracting capital to strategic sectors of the economy.

Various international studies have highlighted that portfolio investment can influence recipient economies in multiple ways. In securities markets, it contributes to increasing liquidity and improving price formation efficiency (Claessens and Rhee 1993; Forbes and Warnock 2012). On a macroeconomic level, these flows have been noted to facilitate international financial integration and diversify funding sources for local firms (Lane and Milesi-Ferretti 2007). FDI can also be channelled through the stock market, producing similar effects (Jeffus 2005). However, potential negative impacts have also been debated, such as increased volatility in emerging economies or the crowding out of other market participants (Anees 2022; Rhee and Wang 2009). Other authors propose a more nuanced view, suggesting that foreign investment tends to target assets that were already sufficiently liquid, further enhancing their liquidity (Marozva and Makoni 2021). In Spain, studies such as those by Hoyo Aparicio (2007), Moreno Castaño (2006), and Ortega Díaz (1998) have underscored the importance of foreign investment in the evolution and modernisation of the stock market, though this line of research remains largely unexplored.

3. Data and methodology

This paper primarily relies on a database built from three main primary sources: annual reports of the Madrid Stock Exchange (1961-1989), Bank of Spain's Cash Register (1990), and Foreign Investment Register (RIE) of the Ministry of Economy and Trade (1991-2007).

The publication *La Bolsa de Madrid*, by the *Ilustre Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa* (Illustrious College of Stockbrokers), provides data from 1961 to 1976. It offers information on foreign investment in equities by sector. From 1977 to 1988, the *Bolsa de Madrid* (Madrid Stock Exchange) published its *Memoria*, maintaining the previous structure and adding the countries of origin of the flows from 1984. In 1989, it was renamed *Informe Anual* (Annual Report). From 1990 onwards, sectoral and country breakdowns ceased, but the detail by investor type increased. In 1994, the name changed to *Informe de Mercado* (Market Report).

From 1988 onwards, the *Boletín Económico de Información Comercial Española* (ICE) provided data from the Bank of Spain's Cash Register, distinguishing between direct and portfolio investment (Iranzo Gutiérrez 1989). Since 1989, figures for the main companies receiving foreign capital were included, allowing for a detailed breakdown (Iranzo Gutiérrez 1990). After 1991, data come from the Ministry of Economy and Trade, and included monthly total flows (Martínez Albadalejo 1992). More years were published in Martínez Albadalejo (1991), Chaves Vidal (1993), and Martínez Albadalejo (1995).

In 1995, the *Boletín de Inversiones Exteriores en Valores Negociables* was introduced. Published quarterly and annually, it was also made with data from the RIE of the Ministry of Economy and Trade. In addition to monthly total flows, these reports are broken down by investor class, country of origin, and sectors of activity, as well as providing information on the destination of the flows —primary or secondary market— companies, and public offerings. Since 1993, the total stock at year-end has been published, for both equities and fixed income, with breakdowns by type of asset, country of origin, and sector of activity.

The annual reports of the Madrid Stock Exchange constitute the only continuous source for the period 1961-1989. This source underestimates total foreign holdings in Spain by omitting investments in the Barcelona, Bilbao, and Valencia exchanges, yet it provides a consistent basis for long-term trends, as Madrid was the dominant channel of foreign portfolio investment (Iranzo Gutiérrez 1988).² However, in 1990, the Madrid Exchange ceased to publish data with the same granularity, leading us to rely on other sources. For that year we have used foreign portfolio investment data from the Bank of Spain's Cash Register. According to Iranzo Gutiérrez (1989), besides data from the four Spanish markets, this source also includes transactions carried out outside the official stock exchanges —such as OTC trades and foreign-market transactions—, whereas the Madrid Stock Exchange only reported transactions within its market. From 1991 onwards, the same criteria were applied in the RIE of the Ministry of Economy and Trade, whose statistics were published in the *Boletín Económico de ICE* (1991-1994) and later in the *Boletín de Inversiones Exteriores en Valores Negociables* (1995-2007). While all these new sources offer more comprehensive coverage, their introduction marks a structural break in the series, as part of the observed increase in foreign investment in 1990 reflects an expansion of statistical coverage —from Madrid to the entire Spanish market and foreign exchanges where Spanish securities are traded— rather than real market growth.³ Despite these differences between sources, they do not affect the consistency of overall trends observed before and after that year.

Notwithstanding the lack of homogeneity, the integration of the sources consulted compensates for their individual shortcomings, enabling their analysis and providing, for the first time, complete and linked series of foreign stock market investment over a long and relevant period of Spain's economic and financial history. The series, where indicated, have been converted into constant 2019 euros using the GDP deflator from the

² While it is difficult to provide a precise estimate, cross-checking with aggregate balance of payments statistics suggests that the figures reported by the Madrid Stock Exchange may underestimate total foreign trading by at least 20–40% in the 1960s-1980s, mainly because they exclude investments channelled through other Spanish exchanges and foreign markets (Iranzo Gutiérrez 1989).

³ In fact, portfolio investment in Spain contracted by 12% in 1990 as the Madrid Stock Market fell by 22.5% (Iranzo Gutiérrez 1989), largely due to the Gulf War and the slowdown of the Spanish economy (Bolsa de Madrid, 1991). Moreover, the 1988 stock market reform caused confusion and lack of precision in the foreign investment data in the reports from 1988 to 1991, when the RIE was established (Garralda Ruiz de Velasco 1996, pp. 533-34). As a result, the figures reported by the Madrid Stock Exchange for those years were probably underestimated.

macroeconomic database of Spain (1954-2019) provided by the Subdirectorate of Economic Analysis and Programming at Banco de España (2021).

4. Foreign investment in the Spanish Stock Exchange (1961-2007)

Figure 1 depicts gross foreign investment in the Spanish stock exchange from 1961 to 2007 in relation to the country's GDP. Meanwhile, Figure 2 shows it as a percentage of total stock trading. Both charts highlight the weight of foreign capital in the Spanish economy and reveal three distinct phases in its evolution: the initially modest yet significant presence of foreign capital during Francoist developmentalism and the transition to democracy (1961–1982); its sharp rise following Spain's negotiations to join the EEC and the securities market reform (1983–1993); and, finally, the stock market boom (1994–2007). Additionally, Figure 3 compares these trends with the annual returns of the Madrid Stock Exchange Total Index (ITBM) over the period. Figure 4 summarises the key historical milestones of the time.

FIGURE 1. Gross foreign capital inflows into the Spanish stock market relative to nominal GDP, 1961-2007 (million euros, logarithmic scale)

Source: Own elaboration based on the sources described in Section 2. Nominal GDP data from the Macroeconomic Database of Spain (1954–2019), Sub-Directorate of Economic Analysis and Programming, Banco de España (2021).

FIGURE 2. Foreign stock exchange trading over total traded, 1961-2007 (%)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the sources described in Section 2.

FIGURE 3 Annual return of the Madrid Stock Exchange Total Index (ITBM), 1961-2007

Source: Own elaboration based on Fernández (2004) and Fernández and Bermejo (2008). Notes: The ITBM calculates annual returns at year-end, factoring in not only price increases of the included securities but also the reinvestment of distributed dividends and capital increases (Bolsa de Madrid 2001).

FIGURE 4. Key historical and stock market events related to foreign investment in stocks (FIS) in Spain, 1961–2007

Source: Own elaboration.

The Madrid Stock Exchange, founded in 1831, is one of the oldest in the world. However, its development has been slow, even considering Spain's sluggish economic growth and its relative backwardness in the European context (Tafunell, 2005). For much of the 19th century, the stock market functioned primarily as a market for financing the Treasury's deficit through public debt issuances, leaving little room for the private sector (Hoyo Aparicio, 2007). This situation persisted until the early 20th century, when bank and industrial company shares began to gain prominence and displaced public securities, though this did not alleviate the narrowness and opacity that characterised the Spanish stock market (Hoyo Aparicio, 2007). The 1930s witnessed a sharp decline in activity and, after the complete shutdown during the Civil War (1936-1939), the Madrid Stock Exchange reopened its doors in March 1940 under a much stricter control. The following two decades were relatively quiet, hampered by the burden of the Francoist autarkic policies. The structural weaknesses of Spain's economic model led to chronic inflation, trade imbalances and stagnation.

Thus, in the economic context of the late 1950s, the Spanish stock market continued to suffer from the structural narrowness that had characterised it throughout its history so the need for urgent reforms to restore stability and growth was clear (Suárez Guinjoan 1982). The 1959 Stabilisation Plan initiated a process of partial liberalisation of the financial system.⁴ In 1961, the convertibility of the peseta was declared, unlocking transactions with foreign markets. This was also the first year in which the Madrid Stock Exchange published statistics on foreign investments. The core of the liberalisation process concluded in 1962, following pressure from international investors and the OECD, which was leading a campaign to liberalize capital movements across its member states. Additionally, the trading of American Depositary Receipts (ADRs) of Spanish shares was authorised in the United States, thereby facilitating their transferability in that market (de la Torre and Rubio-Varas 2015).⁵

Despite the reforms, liquidity shortages, regulatory barriers, and political uncertainty still limited the market's role in corporate financing, making Spain followed a distinct path in the development of its stock market compared to other countries. France, for instance, despite periodic crises, benefited from a stronger institutional framework and deeper integration into European financial networks following the reforms of the 1960s. Its securities market was larger than Spain's, though its role in corporate finance was secondary to bank credit and self-resources (Blancheton, Bonin, and Le Bris 2014).

The Spanish case was closer to that of other Mediterranean countries, such as Italy, where weaker institutions and higher volatility hindered the development of a robust equity

⁴ It established a maximum limit of 50% for foreign ownership in the share capital of Spanish companies. This limit could be exceeded with authorisation from the government.

⁵ ADRs are deposit certificates issued by U.S. banks that represent foreign shares. They can be bought and sold without requiring the actual securities to be transferred, as these can remain deposited in a bank in their country of origin.

market (Aguirre Rodríguez 1976).⁶ While Milan was a larger market than Madrid, both remained marginal within their national financial systems, with the bulk of funding coming from bank credit (Barone 1990; Cuevas 2013). More specifically, public banking institutions played a crucial role in allocating resources for state-led industrial projects, like those of the *Instituto Nacional de Industria* (INI) in Spain (Blasco-Martel, Cuevas, and Riera-Prunera 2023). Consequently, although the stock market included some of the most dynamic sectors of the economy, it did not accurately reflect the overall economic structure. Furthermore, the smaller and medium-sized enterprises, often family-owned, played a predominant role in the economy and were typically absent from the stock exchange, which was instead concentrated in a few large sectors and companies (Cuevas 2013). In fact, gross foreign investment flows into the Spanish stock market did not exceed 1% of the country's GDP until the late 1980s, reflecting the still limited impact of stock market activity on the broader economy (Figure 1). Stock market capitalisation remained modest throughout most of the 20th century, staying close to 30% of GDP in the 1960s before plummeting below 10% during the 1970s crisis, only to recover with financial liberalisation in the late 1980s (Kuvshinov and Zimmermann 2022).

The level of foreign capital in each country also reflected these structural differences. The more developed EEC's stock exchanges attracted more stable capital inflows due to clearer regulations and greater investor confidence, excepting Italy, which, despite occasional surges, experienced substantial local capital flight to foreign mutual funds and remained less appealing for international actors (Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa de Barcelona 1969). France, on the contrary, benefiting from deeper financial integration, was more attractive to international investors, with 18 foreign companies already listed on the Paris stock exchange by 1968 (Commission des Opérations de Bourse 1968).

Spain's slower path toward financial internationalisation limited its immediate benefits, though it began to attract small yet relatively significant amounts of foreign portfolio investment in the early 1960s (Figure 5). This was favoured by the higher economic growth and returns of its stock market compared to other European countries and its low price-to-book ratio (Concha López-Isla 1979). By 1967, foreign stock trading accounted for 44% of the total volume, a threshold that would not be surpassed until the 1990s (Figure 2). In contrast, it represented just 7% in Paris that year and 5-6% in the preceding ones (Commission des Opérations de Bourse 1968). The growth was also driven by the establishment of the first investment funds in 1964.⁷ The increase in trading activity led to sharp price rises, which made the Spanish market more expensive (Figure 3), resulting in a noticeable decline in foreign capital inflows.

⁶ The Italian case has been studied in works like those of CONSOB (2011), Galanti, D'Ambrosio and Guccione (2012), De Luca (2002) or Baia Curioni (2000).

⁷ This was authorised by Decree-Law 7/1964, dated 30 April, on investment companies, mutual funds, and stock exchanges. Collective investment would eventually become, alongside foreign investment, the other major driver of the development of Spain's stock market (Moreno Castaño 2006).

FIGURE 5. Foreign investment flows in Spanish listed shares, 1961-1982 (million euros 2019)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the sources described in Section 2.

The collapse of the Bretton Woods system in 1971 marked a turning point in the international economy. Despite this, there was a slight uptick in foreign capital inflows into Spain, which persisted even during the initial stages of the 1973 oil crisis. In fact, the outbreak of the crisis in October coincided with the annual peak in foreign investment flows (Ilustre Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa 1973; Concha López-Isla 1979). However, this trend came to an end in December (Ilustre Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa 1974). From that moment onwards, factors such as the assassination of Prime Minister Carrero Blanco, doubts about Franco's health and the future of the regime, and the full onset of the crisis in the Spanish economy caused foreign investment to shrink by approximately 75% over the following five years (Ilustre Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa 1975). The beginning of the political transition following the dictator's death in 1975 further heightened uncertainty and mistrust. Foreign capital accounted for an increasingly smaller share of total market trading, reaching just 2.75% in 1976 (Figure 2). This decline prompted the authorisation of foreign investors to own more than 50% of the capital in Spanish companies.⁸

By the late 1970s, signs of nominal recovery began to emerge. The depreciation of the peseta made Spanish stocks more affordable, with foreign participation on the Madrid

⁸ Royal Decree 3099/1976 dated 26 November, on foreign investments in Spain. Its preamble states: "The global economic situation, and particularly the impact of the crisis on capital markets, together with the pressing need of the Spanish economy to boost its investment rate to absorb as much labour as possible, make it advisable to adopt measures aimed at facilitating the entry of foreign capital into the Spanish market".

Stock Exchange reaching 9.5% of the total in 1981.⁹ Additionally, fiscal and regulatory reforms were implemented, such as agreements with several countries to avoid double taxation, which encouraged the inflow of foreign capital (Garralda Ruiz de Velasco 1996).¹⁰ This marked the beginning of a new period (1983–1993), during which the Spanish stock market underwent significant transformation into a modern, developed, and internationalised exchange (Figure 6). Trading volumes and returns increased (Figure 3), accompanied by a notable expansion in foreign investment.

FIGURE 6. Foreign investment flows in Spanish listed shares, 1983-1993 (million euros 2019)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the sources described in Section 2.

With democracy firmly established following the 1982 elections, the primary catalyst for the stock market’s take-off was Spain’s accession to the EEC in 1986. The ITBM index rose by an unprecedented 116%, and non-residents accounted for 18% of trading activity. However, the 1987 stock market crash, which impacted most global exchanges, led to a decline in foreign purchases in Spain. The Spanish market still required institutional reforms to modernise and narrow the gap with other markets (Argandoña 1988). As Table 1 shows, although foreign trading activity was nearing European levels (30%), the stock of foreign ownership of Spanish-listed shares remained modest (12%).¹¹ This suggests

⁹ An average Price-to-Earnings (P/E) ratio of 8 and a Price-to-Book (P/B) ratio of 0.5 (Bolsa de Madrid 1982).

¹⁰ A reform of the Stock Exchange Regulations (Article 35.F) was also implemented to allow foreign stocks to be listed in Spain, along with a fiscal reform aimed at improving income tax deductions for the purchase of securities (Garralda Ruiz de Velasco 1996).

¹¹ The apparent low importance of foreign capital in the U.S., Japanese, and British cases is due to the strong role played by domestic investment in those markets.

that foreign investors were more active and short-term oriented than domestic investors, providing much-needed liquidity to the market. On the other hand, no foreign company had yet chosen Spain as a listing venue, highlighting a significant lag compared to other markets.¹²

TABLE 1. Internationalisation of major stock markets (1988)

Market	Foreign companies listed (% of total)	Weight of foreign investment	
		On capitalisation	On trading
United States	77 (5%)	6%	8%
Japan	112 (7%)	6%	12%
United Kingdom	587 (23%)	7%	15%
Germany	232 (36%)	28%	58%
France	217 (32%)	13%	20%
Switzerland	230 (50%)	32%	46%
Italy	0 (0%)	26%	28%
Holland	228 (49%)	28%	46%
Belgium	151 (45%)	n.a.	n.a.
Sweden	9 (6%)	n.a.	n.a.
Australia	36 (3%)	7%	30%
Spain	0 (0%)	12%	30%

Source: Ontiveros et al. (1991), citing Euromoney (1988) and Choi and Levich (1990).

In this context, the enactment of the Securities Market Law in 1988 provided the final push for its modernisation (Moreno Castaño, 2006).¹³ This law included, among other things, the creation of the National Securities Market Commission (CNMV) as the supervisory government agency, the *Sociedad de Bolsas* (Stock Exchanges Company) and the *Sociedades Rectoras* (Governing Companies) of the four Spanish stock exchanges, the Securities Clearing and Settlement Service —later Iberclear—, and the replacement of the Stockbrokers Agents with the Securities and Brokerage Companies.¹⁴ Additionally, it unified the trading of the Madrid, Barcelona, Bilbao, and Valencia stock exchanges under a continuous market, connected via the CATS electronic system, imported from the Toronto Stock Exchange.¹⁵

The Gulf War (1990), the Spanish economic recession (1992-1993), and the European Monetary System crisis (1992) caused a certain stagnation, which is reflected in the final years of this period. Nevertheless, foreign investment continued to act as a driver for stock

¹² Italy was another market without listed foreign companies. The country’s macroeconomic situation and high risk were combined with a structurally weak stock market, poor transparency, low protection for small investors, restrictive regulation and limited liberalisation (Colli 2009, p. 267). Similar problems to those faced by the Spanish stock market.

¹³ Law 24/1988, of 28 July.

¹⁴ This also allowed the parallel development of private banking in Spain, as explained by Puig and García Ruiz (2020).

¹⁵ This system was replaced in 1995 by the SIBE, developed by the Madrid Stock Exchange itself.

market activity. The period of major reforms ended in 1993 with the Maastricht Treaty, which established the roadmap for the European Economic and Monetary Union and consolidated the liberalisation of capital movements in all member countries.¹⁶ European economic integration was a key factor in understanding why foreign flows into the Spanish stock market increased by 158% that year. By the end of this second period, foreign investment already represented 40% of the total trading of Spanish stocks (Galmés 1993), with nearly 30% taking place in foreign exchanges (Bolsa de Madrid 1993).

The third and final stage took place between 1994 and 2007 (Figure 7). During this time, the Spanish stock market deepened its transformation and saw significant growth in trading, while keeping attractive returns (Figure 3). The stock of shares in foreign hands reached around 35%, fluctuating at this level until the end of the period (BME 2024b). The market gained a major boost in its internationalisation with the exponential growth of foreign investment, initially driven by the privatisation of large public companies. This process helped improve overall liquidity and strengthened Spain's position in the global financial scene (Bel and Comesaña 2001). Indeed, the exit of the public sector—which had kept its portfolio inactive—from the shareholding allowed for an increase in trading, with the trading/capitalisation ratio rising from 25% in 1990 to 60% in 1999 (García Coto, Sánchez García, and Beiras Escudero 2010). Additionally, the ownership structure of Spanish companies changed, with public administrations reducing their stake from 17% of the stock in 1992 to just 0.2% in 2000. In this period Spanish banks also reduced their portfolios of industrial shares, lowering its participation in the total stock of equity from 16% in 1992 to 7% in 2007 (Tortella and García Ruiz 2015; BME 2024b). Overall, portfolio investment gained relative weight in the market, reaching a historic 99% of the total foreign investment in 1998 (Ministerio de Economía y Hacienda 1999).

During the 1990s, fixed-income securities also regained foreign interest.¹⁷ The restrictive policies of Francoism and the poor economic situation in the early years of democracy limited investment to very modest amounts. However, Spain's entry into the EEC provided the necessary confidence for a surge, and in 1987, foreign flows into government debt surpassed those into equities for the first time. From then on, there was a gradual rise. By 2002, the significant increase in private debt issuances meant that foreign investment in equities was no longer the majority in Spain's stock markets (Figure 8). The expansion of the Spanish economy thus altered the destination of foreign capital.

¹⁶ The liberalisation of capital movements was previously carried out with the European Council Directive 88/61/EEC of 24 July 1988, which entered into force on 1 July 1990.

¹⁷ Foreign investment in government debt, especially from France, was common in the 19th century and the first third of the 20th century (Broder 1981; Tascón Fernández 2008).

FIGURE 7. Foreign investment flows in Spanish listed shares, 1994-2007 (million euros 2019)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the sources described in Section 2.

FIGURE 8. Stock of foreign investments in marketable securities, 1992-2007 (relative %)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Table A1 in appendix.

With the new millennium, a period of net foreign investment outflows in stocks was accompanied by a notable increase in trading volume (Figure 7). This situation, seemingly contradictory with the equity figures (Figure 8) and the market's good performance in

those years, can be explained by the bullish behaviour of the stock market.¹⁸ In most cases, the selling prices were higher than the buying prices. Therefore, non-residents, by realizing their capital gains, generated a greater selling balance. The bullish trend was only interrupted by events such as the bursting of the dot-com bubble, the 9/11 attacks, or the accounting scandals of Enron and MCI.

In 2007, on the eve of the Great Recession, gross foreign investment inflows reached historic highs, tripling those of just five years earlier and amounting to 96% of Spain's real GDP (Figure 1). It was the swan song of an era of great prosperity, characterised by a smaller presence of the public sector among shareholders and greater internationalisation with record levels of foreign participation. The emergence of the housing bubble and the expansion of credit generated an “irrational exuberance” in the Spanish stock market during the final years of the period, in line with what was happening in other markets such as Wall Street (Shiller 2001). Spain had completed its integration into the international financial landscape (Gómez Biscarri and Pérez de Gracia 2004).

5. Sectors and companies

Figure 9 shows foreign investment by sector of activity with its percentage weights, and Table 2 lists, from 1989 onwards, the names of the most traded companies by foreigners.

FIGURE 9. Gross inflows of foreign investment in Spanish listed shares by five-year period and sector of activity, 1961-2007 (% of the total)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Table A2 in appendix.

¹⁸ For the period 1993-2003, Madrid achieved an average annual return with dividends of 13%, compared to 11% for New York and -2% for Tokyo (Ministerio de Economía y Hacienda 2004b).

From a sectoral perspective, foreign investment in the Spanish stock market can be classified into four main categories. The first includes the sectors with the greatest historical attraction for foreign capital, primarily banking and energy. The second corresponds to traditional sectors linked to Spain's industrialisation, which have become less relevant in the national economy and have lost appeal for foreigners. The third category includes sectors related to the expansion of information and communication technologies, a recent development. Finally, a secondary group in terms of attracting foreign flows, which includes consumption and real estate.

TABLE 2. Foreign investment in shares by five-year period and company, 1989-2007 (million euros 2019)

	Company	Investment	%	Disinvestment	%	Net balance
1989-1993	Telefónica de España	9,339	8	7,174	9	2,165
	Repsol	8,883	8	4,792	6	4,091
	Banco Santander	5,425	5	3,408	4	2,017
	Iberdrola	5,029	4	3,950	5	1,079
	Banco Popular Español	4,443	4	3,740	5	703
	BBV (Banco Bilbao Vizcaya)	3,760	3	3,253	4	507
	Cía, Valenciana de Cementos Portland	3,471	3	1,937	2	1,534
	Endesa	3,439	3	3,413	4	26
	Central bank	2,863	3	1,249	2	1,614
	Corporación Bancaria de España	2,860	3	1,026	1	1,834
	Total, Top 10	49,512	44	33,941	43	15,571
Others	62,440	56	45,510	57	16,930	
1994-1998	Telefónica	77,211	20	71,819	19	5,393
	Endesa	41,885	11	35,161	10	6,724
	Banco Santander	34,473	9	35,638	10	-1,165
	Repsol	33,883	9	34,768	9	-885
	BBV (Banco Bilbao Vizcaya)	26,186	7	27,233	7	-1,047
	Argentaria	23,796	6	20,730	6	3,066
	Iberdrola	23,298	6	22,161	6	1,138
	Banco Popular Español	13,620	4	14,696	4	-1,076
	Banco Central Hispano	12,485	3	11,090	3	1,395
	Tabacalera	7,123	2	6,393	2	730
	Total, Top 10	293,360	77	279,688	76	14,272
Others	88,830	23	88,809	24	21	
1999-2003	Telefónica	363,593	25	396,512	26	-32,919
	Banco Santander Central Hispano	217,090	15	229,998	15	-12,908
	BBVA (Banco Bilbao Vizcaya Argentaria)	168,691	12	179,893	12	-11,201
	Repsol YPF	128,087	9	133,937	9	-5,851
	Endesa	107,158	7	112,324	7	-5,166
	Iberdrola	59,982	4	64,833	4	-4,850
	Altadis	41,700	3	44,029	3	-2,329
	Banco Popular Español	40,450	3	42,447	3	-1,998

Company		Investment	%	Disinvestme nt	%	Net balance
	Terra Networks	25,516	2	32,958	2	-7,442
	Inditex	22,116	2	20,734	1	1,382
	Total, Top 10	1,174,382	81	1,257,665	81	-83,283
	Others	282,607	19	290,764	19	-8,157
2004-2007	Banco Santander	551,258	20	554,168	20	-2,910
	Telefónica	444,958	16	454,249	16	-9,291
	BBVA (Banco Bilbao Vizcaya Argentaria)	412,327	15	418,550	15	-6,223
	Endesa	238,086	9	228,066	8	10,020
	Repsol YPF	209,489	7	216,063	8	-6,574
	Iberdrola	162,070	6	171,145	6	-9,076
	Banco Popular Español	64,777	2	67,413	2	-2,636
	Altadis	63,027	2	64,699	2	-1,672
	Inditex	50,726	2	49,895	2	832
	ACS (Acts. de Construcción y Servicios)	34,178	1	36,936	1	-2,758
	Total, Top 10	2,230,897	80	2,261,184	80	-30,287
	Others	564,366	20	568,019	20	-3,653

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the Madrid Stock Exchange and the Ministry of Trade (1989-2007) described in section 2.

Banking was one of the main protagonists in the history of the stock market and the Spanish economy during the 20th century.¹⁹ It drove the country's industrial development through credit and investment, although the monopolistic nature of the banking-industry relationship led to the displacement of other actors —such as the stock market itself— from its role in financing growth, at times hindering proper resource allocation (Tortella and Núñez 2011, p. 493). Foreign investment in banking through the stock market played a significant role, initially driven by a low price-to-book value ratio (Concha López-Isla 1979). On average, it accounted for 25% of gross flows until 1985. However, the sector's strong regulation, despite a timid liberalisation with the Law of Bases for the Organisation of Credit and Banking, reduced its appeal and hindered capital attraction (Pons Brías 2011). Additionally, the 1970s crisis plunged the sector into a deep restructuring, which brought foreign participation to historic lows.

The quantitative leap in foreign presence in the financial sector occurred with Spain's entry into the EEC and the listing of banks and other large Spanish companies on international markets (Table 3). Only the pioneers Banco Central and Banco Popular preceded this significant trend led by Banco Santander, the only one —along with Telefónica— to be listed on five of the major global stock exchanges. The growing foreign interest was also reflected in acquisitions of local entities, such as the purchase of 84% of Banco de Finanzas by the American Chase Manhattan (Bolsa de Madrid 1986) or the acquisition of Bankoia by Crédit Agricole. This trend was replicated in other parts of

¹⁹ For a study on the history of banking in Spain and its importance on the economy, see Tortella and García Ruiz (2015).

the financial sector, particularly in insurance. The fragmentation of this business into small companies allowed operations such as the acquisition of the historic La Unión y El Fénix by the French AGF.

TABLE 3. First Spanish companies listed on major foreign stock exchanges (year of start)

Company	New York	Tokyo	London	Frankfurt	Paris
Banco Popular	—	—	—	—	1973
Banco Central	1983	—	1986	1963	1983
Banco Hispano	—	—	—	1981	—
Banco Santander	1987	1990	1985	1981	1984
BBV	1988	—	1985	1981	—
Telefónica	1987	1985	1985	1985	1985
Endesa	1988	—	—	—	—
Repsol	1989	—	—	—	—

Source: Ontiveros *et al.* (1991).

During the stock market boom (1994-2007), banking stocks played a key role in a period when mergers and acquisitions began to define the history of the sector. The most relevant ones, which occurred in 1999, were the merger of BBV with the privatised Argentaria and that of Santander with Banco Central Hispano. The latter accounted for 12% of foreign trading that year. The economies of scale achieved by Spanish banks, also immersed in a process of internationalisation towards Latin America, were positively received by foreigners. The sector entered the early years of the 21st century with fewer players but occupying a prominent place in the attention of foreign investors (Table 2).

Energy companies, in turn, have had a somewhat pioneering role and a distinct weight in attracting foreign capital. In the early 1960s, Iberduero, 3% owned by General Electric since 1928, became the first Spanish company to have its ADRs traded on the American market (de la Torre and Rubio-Varas 2015). This early internationalisation, combined with public investment in energy infrastructure and increased industrial demand, attracted some foreign investment flows. Interest in this sector at an early stage seems to support Tortella and Núñez's (2011, pp. 425-429) view of it as an attractive market whose challenges were more related to regulatory excess than to resource availability. However, even before the oil crisis, there was a contraction in gross investment, which persisted until 1983, when it rose by 70%. Alongside banking, the electricity sector showed the least upward movement that year, reaffirming foreign interest in relatively cheap stocks.²⁰ Nevertheless, it was the privatisation of the sector that ultimately drove foreign purchases. Endesa's privatisation began in 1988, followed by Repsol's IPO a year later, the largest offering in Spain up to that time. Many non-residents participated, making it the most traded company that year. Subsequently, British Petroleum launched a public takeover bid for Petromed, while the French Elf made a similar move for Cepsa.

²⁰ A strategy that proved to be successful, as electricity companies rose in price by 90% the following year (Bolsa de Madrid 1985).

The gradual sale of state-owned energy companies and the creation of a more efficient and liberalised regulatory framework allowed new players to enter the market during the 1990s (Beato Blanco 2005). Among the most significant transactions were additional public offerings (APOs) by Repsol and Endesa, which at times accounted for nearly 20% of all foreign capital flows into listed shares (Table 2). Over time, and well into the 21st century, the sector received a fresh boost from investment in renewable energy—led by Iberdrola—and the largest FDI transaction in the history of the Spanish market: the 2007 acquisition of Endesa by Italy’s Enel, involving an outlay of more than €28 billion.

After the historically dominant sectors, the industrial and construction sectors stand out as the second group, following a pattern of decline like Spain’s own industrial restructuring. Once the most significant sector for foreign presence during the Franco era, it progressively lost prominence, especially from the 1990s onward. The regime’s strong push for industrialisation concentrated numerous heavy industry projects under the National Institute of Industry (INI). Some of these projects quickly attracted foreign interest. In the 1960s, foreign investment flows into the sector began to increase, particularly in chemicals. However, the automotive industry drove the peak in foreign investment and trading on the stock exchange, reached in 1967 (Figures 2, 6 and 9), a record that would remain unmatched for decades. This zenith can be attributed, on one hand, to the increase in the Italian FIAT’s stake in SEAT to 36% of its share capital, causing the INI to lose its dominant position in the company (Catalán i Vidal 2006, p. 160). On the other hand, it was driven by a capital increase in FASA-Renault, where the French group expanded its position (Fernández de Sevilla 2014, p. 157). Foreigners required more control to increase investment and begin to export part of the production (Fernández de Sevilla, 2014; García Ruiz and Santos Redondo 2001). This sector continued to attract significant FDI until the early 1970s (Catalán i Vidal 2006, p. 176).

However, the oil crisis dealt a severe blow, and foreign investment in the stock market contracted sharply. Nevertheless, in relative terms, heavy industry accounted for nearly one-third of investment flows by the end of the decade, due to the mass exodus of capital from smaller sectors grouped under “Others” category in Figure 9. The automotive industry, the only industrial activity to maintain a steady investment pace, gradually ceded its leadership to civil engineering. This shift became particularly significant from 1988 onwards, coinciding with a major wave of infrastructure investment. Spain was modernizing in preparation for hosting the Seville Expo and the Barcelona Summer Olympics. Spanish engineering firms—such as Acciona, ACS, and Sacyr—thived and embarked on successful international expansions, making them highly attractive to foreign investors (Álvaro-Moya 2009).

From the 1990s onwards, the industrial sector rapidly lost significance, coinciding with Spain’s deindustrialisation and a slowdown in the construction of new infrastructure. As in other activities, the most notable foreign-led operations involved mergers and acquisitions, such as the French company Lafarge’s purchase of the cement manufacturer Asland or the Swiss group Glencore’s acquisition of the mining company Asturiana de

Zinc. Cement became one of the pioneering subsectors to attract investment from emerging economies, exemplified by Portugal's Cimpor entering Corporación Noroeste and Mexico's Cemex acquiring Valenciana de Cementos. Meanwhile, the takeover of Sociedad Española de Oxígeno by France's Air Liquide and a subsequent public tender offer for Argón resulted in industrial gases becoming the first stock market subsector entirely controlled by foreign investors. Additionally, some privatisations saw significant foreign involvement, such as Aceralia's.

In the 21st century, the relative rise of new sectors pushed industry and construction to the margins of foreign stock market activity, reducing their share to around 5%. The only exception was engineering, which experienced a resurgence thanks to a new wave of public infrastructure investment on an international scale, effectively capitalised on by Spanish engineering firms (Chislett 2014).

A third group gaining prominence in the Spanish stock markets comprises technology and telecommunications. Historically, Telefónica has been the sector's leading representative, though it attracted limited foreign investment due to its status as a mostly state-owned company in a heavily regulated industry. In fact, in 1975, it carried out the largest capital increase in the history of the stock exchange at that time yet still recorded net outflows of foreign capital (Ilustre Colegio de Agentes de Cambio y Bolsa 1976). This situation shifted in 1985 when Telefónica was listed on four major international stock exchanges, expanded to five two years later (Table 3). These listings facilitated non-residents' access to its shares, and, together with its progressive privatisation in the mid-1990s, drove a significant increase in foreign investment. From that point on, Telefónica became the leading company in foreign trading almost every year, at times accounting for over a quarter of total flows (Table 2) and even peaking at 35% in 2000 (Ministerio de Economía y Hacienda 2001).

Meanwhile, in the closing years of the 20th century, new players emerged on the stock market, driven by the revolution in information and communication technologies. Foreign presence was notable in companies such as Amadeus and the privatised Indra Sistemas, as well as in others like Terra Networks, which was eventually acquired by Telefónica following the burst of the dot-com bubble (Cuevas 2013).

The final prominent group comprises consumer companies, which have traditionally played a significant role in the Spanish economy. This group includes subsectors such as food, retail, textiles, and monopolies. However, in the stock market it has rarely attracted substantial attention from foreign capital. After a modest performance during the Franco era, the oil crisis severely impacted the sector, driving investment to historic lows. In the early 1980s, foreign investors shifted their focus toward recovering cyclical sectors, such as banking, utilities, and the automotive industry, as previously discussed. Consumption followed this trend, particularly in retail, with Galerías Preciados accounting for a significant portion of non-resident activity.

However, growth fell short of expectations, and Spain's economic challenges—including unemployment, inflation, and high interest rates—persisted, leading to renewed declines in foreign investment (Bolsa de Madrid 1982). The wave of mergers and acquisitions in the following years was evident in the sector, facilitated by its structure of family-owned businesses. The most significant privatisation was that of Tabacalera, which was rebranded as Altadis. Shortly thereafter, it merged with the French company Seita, becoming one of the most actively traded companies by foreign investors on the Spanish stock exchange (Table 2).

In short, the economic sectors attracting foreign investment in the Spanish stock exchange have evolved alongside the country's economic history. Nevertheless, banking and energy have consistently maintained a prominent position in foreign capital, while investment flows have become increasingly concentrated in a smaller number of stocks (Table 2). By 2007, just five companies—Banco Santander, Telefónica, BBVA, Endesa, and Repsol—accounted for two-thirds of gross capital inflows (Ministerio de Economía y Hacienda 2007).

6. Countries and investor classes

Foreign investment in the Spanish stock market has evolved significantly over time, shaped by Spain's economic opening and financial liberalisation. This section first examines the main foreign investors before the democratic transition, followed by an analysis of the 1984-2007 period, highlighting the distinct roles played by different countries and their financial institutions.

Although official statistics on foreign investment by country were not published before 1984, a 1974 report from the Barcelona College of Stockbrokers provides valuable insights into the nationality of investors during the developmentalist period. The data suggest a clear distinction between countries that predominantly engaged in foreign portfolio investment and those that focused on FDI. Switzerland, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom emerge as the most significant financial investors, with a strong presence in portfolio investment. Their role aligns with their well-established financial sectors and historical ties to international capital flows. In 1961, during the ongoing liberalisation process in Spain, almost half of portfolio investment came from the Swiss investment fund ESPAC, specialised in Spanish equity and promoted by *Union de Banques Suisses* (UBS) (de la Torre and Rubio-Varas 2015). It was primarily directed towards the industrial and banking sectors, taking advantage of the relative discount at which these stocks were trading.

In contrast, industrial powers like the United States and Germany stand out as major sources of FDI, reflecting their direct involvement in corporate investments rather than stock market activity. France, by comparison, maintained a more balanced profile, combining both direct and portfolio investments. The significance of American capital during the Franco regime is well-documented (Tascón Fernández 2008). The 1953 Madrid Agreements paved the way for economic aid, loans, and direct investments, while

the gradual financial liberalisation following the 1959 Stabilisation Plan also led to increased stock market activity.²¹ This was particularly facilitated by the issuance of ADRs for Spanish shares on Wall Street. Nonetheless, the 1970s crisis had a significant impact on the United States, which gradually lost its relative importance in the Madrid Stock Exchange. Simultaneously, Spanish authorities began to increasingly look towards Europe, following the direction set by Minister Castiella (Oreja Aguirre and Sánchez Mantero 2007).

On the other hand, with Spain's integration process into the European Economic Community (EEC) and the stock market reform, foreign investment in the Madrid Stock Exchange became increasingly concentrated among a few key regions. Between 1984 and 2007, around 98% of total foreign inflows originated from EU-15 countries, the European Free Trade Association (EFTA), and the United States (Figure 10). The remaining share came mainly from other OECD members, Latin America, and the Gulf states.

The United Kingdom has by far contributed the largest share of flows to Spanish stock markets. Its investment was predominant from the mid-1990s and reached nearly 60% of the total just before the Great Recession. This dominance is attributed to its position as an international financial centre, channelling flows from other parts of the world, such as the United States or Japan. British banks, led by Barclays, quickly made their appearance in Spain after the securities market reform of the late 1980s. British companies also joined the wave of acquisitions of Spanish companies, many of them former public enterprises, such as the purchase of Tabacalera by Imperial Tobacco in 2007.

Although its share decreased, the United States remained a crucial player throughout the period, with banks such as JP Morgan, Bank of America, and Citicorp being some of the main financial intermediaries on the Spanish stock market. Following the securities market reforms of the 1980s and the abolition of traditional stockbrokers, these banks directly entered the market by establishing foreign brokerage and securities firms. American capital also played a role in the significant wave of mergers and acquisitions involving local companies and participated in primary market operations, including the stock market listings of Inditex and Iberia. Additionally, New York-based investment funds, such as the Spain Fund created in 1989 by Alliance Bernstein, demonstrated increasing interest in Spanish equities. Thus, the United States positioned itself as a vital partner for the Spanish stock market, accounting for over 17% of total foreign investment flows in some years.

FIGURE 10. Main countries investing in Spanish stock market, 1984-2007 (darker shades indicate higher investment flows)

²¹ The 1953 Madrid Agreements between Spain and the United States marked a turning point in the country's international economic relations. In exchange for military bases on Spanish territory, the U.S. provided economic aid and loans, which helped stabilize the Spanish economy and set the stage for the gradual economic opening that culminated in the 1959 Stabilisation Plan (Viñas 2003).

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Table A3 in appendix.

France maintained its historical position as a key financial partner, with its investments largely directed towards banking, energy, and industrial firms. French financial institutions also established brokerage firms in Spain, such as Kepler Chevreux and Société Générale.

German banks, also issuers of foreign investment during the Franco era, played a significant role during the 1980s, channelling one-third of the stock market transactions, particularly Deutsche Bank and Commerzbank (Bolsa de Madrid 1991). The latter became, in 1990, the first foreign company to list on the Madrid Stock Exchange, marking a milestone in the internationalisation of the market from the supply side. It was immediately followed by Volkswagen, which had recently acquired control of SEAT. Nonetheless, the country gradually declined in relative importance over time, as did Switzerland.

In the rest of the issuing countries, the Netherlands stands out in first place. As a major financial centre in Europe, investment funds headquartered there played an important role, such as the Goya Fund, created in 1989 and specialising in Spanish equities. In second place, Italy was involved in some significant FDI operations, such as the acquisition of Sindicatos de Banqueros de Barcelona by Monte dei Paschi di Siena in 1993 or, as previously mentioned, the takeover bid by Enel for Endesa in 2007. Finally, in recent decades, investment flows from emerging countries, such as Portugal, have been increasingly observed.

The investment originating from Belgium and Luxembourg can largely be explained by Figure 11. As previously mentioned, foreign financial intermediaries —especially banks— have played a significant role in the Spanish stock market, concentrating nearly 90% of total foreign flows. The majority of Belgian and Luxembourg investment comes from non-credit financial institutions. These countries host some of the most important brokerage and securities firms in Europe, as well as several clearing and settlement houses, such as Euroclear.

Indeed, financial intermediaries have generated a significant portion of the trading activity in their role as market makers and as part of their ordinary investment and private banking businesses (Puig and García Ruiz 2020). The remaining actors—such as companies, investment and pension funds, or individuals—seem relatively unimportant in comparison. However, as their name suggests, financial intermediaries operate on behalf of third parties who may belong to these groups, but do not appear in official statistics since they are not the ones executing the transactions in the market.

FIGURE 11. Gross inflows of foreign investment in Spanish listed shares by five-year period and type of investor, 1991-2007 (%)

Source: Own elaboration based on data from Table A4 in appendix. From the innermost to the outermost ring, the periods are: 1991-1995, 1996-2000, 2001-2005, and 2006-2007.

In summary, although American capital was and continues to be very important in the history of the Spanish stock market, the European Union has gained relevance, eventually surpassing 85% of the total on the eve of the Great Recession. The Maastricht Treaty liberalised financial transactions, and the adoption of the euro eliminated exchange rate risks. These two milestones have been crucial facilitators of capital inflows from these countries. Additionally, 99% of the flows originated from OECD members (Ministerio de Economía y Hacienda 2008). These figures reflect how the dynamics of economic integration have reshaped the international profile of the Spanish stock market.

7. Conclusions

This paper aims to expand existing knowledge on the flows and dynamics of foreign investment in the Spanish stock market between 1961 and 2007. Despite the limitations and fragmentation of the available sources, we have constructed a novel database that enables analysis of the relationship between the arrival of non-resident investors and the process of development, modernisation, and globalisation of the Madrid stock exchange.²²

The historical series highlights the drastic change in the significance of foreign investment in the Spanish stock market over time. In the mid-1970s, foreign investors accounted for barely 2.5% of total trading, and their gross inflows equalled less than 1% of GDP. However, by 2007, these figures reached 62% and 96%, respectively, underscoring the extraordinary weight that foreign capital had acquired in the country's economy and financial system. In doing so, this study adds a new dimension to Spain's financial openness and integration into the international context, which has previously been interpreted through the lens of FDI (Puig and Álvaro-Moya 2015).

The period-based analysis reveals that foreign trading played a more significant role in the Spanish stock exchange during the late Francoism than previously assumed. Despite the institutional and technological lag compared to other European markets, as noted by Ontiveros et al. (1991), the period before the oil crisis should not be underestimated. Until 1968, foreign trading surpassed 40% of the total, only to then decline drastically to minimal levels in the 1970s. Although the negotiated volume was still small, the presence of foreign investment was highly significant, suggesting a potential catalyst for the transformation and modernisation of the market. Foreign actors likely brought techniques, experience, and investment strategies from the more advanced Western countries, promoting higher standards of ethics and information transparency (Garralda Ruiz de Velasco 1996; Hoyo Aparicio 2007).

The economic and stock market reforms of the 1980s and Spain's integration into the EEC helped consolidate foreign investment and reduce transaction costs. In this way, the Spanish case highlights the need to build and maintain an open and modern institutional environment, as well as the positive role of economic and monetary integration agreements in promoting foreign investment. Thus, in line with Moreno Castaño (2006), this work emphasizes institutional change as a driving force for growth and openness in the stock market.

Regarding the recipients of foreign investment, the series shows distinctive sectoral and corporate patterns over time. From a sectoral perspective, banking and energy consistently remained the traditional destinations of foreign capital. In contrast, other sectors evolved in line with the Spanish business cycle. The decline of industry and

²² It should be recalled that part of the sharp increase observed after 1990 reflects the expansion of statistical coverage—capturing flows across all Spanish exchanges and even foreign markets—rather than a sudden surge in market activity (see Section 2).

construction, alongside the rise of technology and telecommunications, mirrors the process of de-industrialisation and Spain's transformation into a service-based economy during the late 20th century.

At the corporate level, the data reveal that trading became increasingly concentrated in a smaller group of large companies. By the early 21st century, only ten companies absorbed more than 80% of the gross foreign capital inflows into the stock market. These stocks were already established and liquid prior to the arrival of non-residents, whose participation further improved their liquidity, as Marozva and Makoni (2021) suggested. Yet our findings diverge from those of Anees (2022) or Rhee and Wang (2009), who observed in other contexts that the entry of foreign investors displaced domestic actors. In the Spanish case, not only was there no such crowding-out, but we indeed observed a parallel development in domestic stock market participation (Moreno Castaño 2006). Additionally, the banking sector experienced notable growth during this period (Tafunell 2005; Tortella and García Ruiz 2015), suggesting a dynamic of complementarity, rather than substitution, between local and foreign actors.

The analysis by countries shows that the investment was primarily institutional, originating from traditional partners such as the United Kingdom, the United States, and major European Union members. These are large capital-exporting economies with significant political, economic, and commercial ties to Spain. The British case is particularly striking, as it has consistently accounted for more than half of the total foreign investment flows, making it the largest capital issuer at least since the 1970s. This contrasts with the relatively limited attention it has received in academic literature compared to other countries such as the United States or France (Castro and Sánchez 2015; Puig 2002; Puig and Álvaro-Moya 2018). This disparity can be partially explained by the greater scholarly focus on FDI, which has emphasised the transfer of technology, managerial expertise, and access to international markets. By comparison, British investors have played an eminently financial role, making it more challenging to capture their more intangible impact on the local market. As a major international financial hub, however, the United Kingdom may have acted not only as a conduit for capital but also as a transmitter of knowledge, fostering the professionalisation of intermediaries and the adoption of more sophisticated investment practices (Bussière and Cassis 2005; Cassis 2010).

This work can serve as a foundation for further research. Future work could explore in greater depth the role of foreign actors in introducing new investment strategies or standards of information and financial transparency. On the other hand, case studies focused on specific sectors or companies could offer a better understanding of the role of stock market investment as a driver of economic and business activity. Analysing these underexplored dimensions of the stock market can contribute to decision-making that promotes its future prosperity and development.

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Author contribution statement

Álvaro González: methodology, framework, dataset, investigation, formal analysis, writing, visualization. Águeda Gil: framework, dataset, supervision, writing. Elena San Román: methodology, framework, supervision, writing. Víctor Gómez: formal analysis, visualization, supervision.

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Appendix

This section provides comprehensive tables containing the detailed data referenced throughout this paper, offering a more granular view of the information presented in the main body of the text and allowing for in-depth analysis and further exploration of the findings.

TABLE A1. Stock of foreign investments in marketable securities, 1992-2007 (2019 euros and relative %)

YEAR	EQUITY	%	PUBLIC DEBT	%	PRIVATE DEBT	%
1992	38,642	63	20,947	34	1,909	3
1993	61,848	52	53,718	45	3,384	3
1994	59,615	57	39,640	38	4,784	5
1995	65,957	57	43,506	38	6,404	6
1996	86,255	56	60,551	39	7,999	5
1997	116,829	62	63,696	34	8,122	4
1998	163,033	69	68,402	29	5,472	2
1999	229,075	64	115,039	32	13,007	4
2000	239,198	60	130,824	33	29,161	7
2001	223,853	58	134,072	35	29,726	8
2002	154,703	42	152,642	42	57,000	16
2003	195,913	41	175,877	37	108,468	23
2004	231,822	41	158,388	28	178,922	31
2005	245,516	36	174,996	25	269,514	39
2006	286,061	36	150,842	19	364,624	45
2007	332,282	39	161,831	19	347,568	41
TOTAL	2,730,602	47	1,704,973	29	1,436,065	24

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the sources described in Section 2.

TABLE A2. Gross inflows of foreign investment in Spanish listed shares by five-year period and sector of activity, 1961-2007 (million euros 2019 and % of the total)

PERIOD	FIN		ENE		CON		INC		TTE		RES		OTR		TOTAL
	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €	%	M. €
1961-1965	318	15	338	15	214	10	638	29	59	3	96	4	519	24	2,182
1966-1970	466	18	97	4	95	4	1,154	44	40	2	45	2	735	28	2,632
1971-1975	431	29	71	5	161	11	374	25	43	3	24	2	405	27	1,507
1976-1980	285	41	99	14	45	6	226	32	24	3	13	2	6	1	697
1981-1985	605	24	371	15	126	5	480	19	866	34	57	2	20	1	2,525
1986-1990	19,262	31	6,627	11	3,832	6	23,521	38	6,410	10	779	1	1,905	3	62,335
1991-1995	45,377	32	42,535	30	6,580	5	19,536	14	19,885	14	3,188	2	4,765	3	141,865
1996-2000	273,803	31	221,469	25	35,913	4	37,286	4	281,517	32	6,826	1	28,927	3	885,741
2001-2005	708,119	37	458,468	24	129,116	7	94,974	5	390,127	20	18,716	1	103,588	5	1,903,110
2006-2007	691,360	37	494,160	27	140,283	8	108,614	6	317,870	17	31,647	2	69,568	4	1,853,501
TOTAL	1,740,026	36	1,224,235	25	316,364	7	286,803	6	1,016,840	21	61,390	1	210,439	4	4,856,095

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the Madrid Stock Exchange and the Ministry of Trade (1961-2007) described in section 2. Notes: OTR: Others; FIN: Financial services (banking, insurance and investment); ENE: Oil and energy; CON: Consumer goods and services; INC: Basic materials, industry and construction; TTE: Technology and telecommunications; RES: Real estate services. Classification inspired by BME (2024a).

TABLE A3. Gross inflows of foreign investment in Spanish listed shares by five-year period and country of origin, 1984-2007 (millions of euros 2019 and % of the total)

COUNTRY	1984-1988		1989-1993		1994-1998		1999-2003		2004-2007		TOTAL	
	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%
United Kingdom	13,482	41	45,092	43	198,513	51	811,973	55	1,628,150	57	2,697,210	56
United States	2,586	8	17,422	17	54,722	14	204,577	14	293,459	10	572,765	12
France	2,911	9	8,127	8	40,265	10	151,895	10	325,112	11	528,311	11
Belgium/Luxembourg	939	3	6,166	6	28,016	7	99,433	7	184,075	6	318,630	7
Germany	5,545	17	3,681	4	21,272	5	74,292	5	90,685	3	195,474	4
Netherlands	557	2	5,473	5	6,955	2	24,260	2	99,876	4	137,120	3
Switzerland	4,580	14	6,890	7	15,395	4	33,033	2	62,300	2	122,197	3
Italy	120	0	1,305	1	3,156	1	15,623	1	84,385	3	104,589	2
Portugal	52	0	663	1	7,785	2	17,566	1	13,910	0	39,976	1
Others	2,151	7	9,259	9	13,951	4	33,470	2	79,862	3	133,233	3
TOTAL	32,923	100	104,077	100	390,032	100	1,466,122	100	2,856,353	100	4,849,506	100

TABLE A4. Gross inflows of foreign investment in Spanish listed shares by five-year period and type of investor, 1991-2007 (millions of euros in 2019 and % of the total)

INVESTOR CLASS	1991-1995		1996-2000		2001-2005		2006-2010		TOTAL	
	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%	MM. €	%
Credit financial intermediary	82,739	58	593,642	67	1,217,415	64	1,092,260	59	2,986,056	62
Non-credit financial intermediary	30,371	21	218,729	25	494,772	26	641,532	35	1,385,404	29
Private non-financial companies	19,997	14	32,360	4	53,755	3	68,856	4	174,968	4
Investment and pension funds	1,945	1	12,514	1	100,012	5	19,941	1	134,412	3
Individuals	1,788	0	19,957	2	17,527	1	2,008	0	40,000	1
Insurance companies	508	1	2,557	0	4,651	0	706	0	9,702	0
Other investors	4,518	3	5,983	1	14,976	1	24,512	1	49,989	1
TOTAL	141,865	100	885,741	100	1,903,109	100	2,004,696	100	4,780,531	100

Source: Own elaboration based on data from the Madrid Stock Exchange and the Ministry of Trade (1984-2007) described in section 2.

La inversió estrangera i el desenvolupament de la borsa de valors a Espanya (1961-2007)

RESUM

Aquest article reconstrueix les dinàmiques de la inversió estrangera a la borsa espanyola entre 1961 i 2007, explorant aquesta dimensió menys coneguda de la globalització financera i la modernització del mercat a Espanya. Mitjançant la construcció d'una base de dades innovadora, analitza les tendències d'inversió per sectors, empreses, països d'origen i tipus d'inversors, oferint una visió detallada de l'evolució del capital estranger durant la reintegració d'Espanya en l'economia global. Els resultats posen de manifest la concentració de la inversió estrangera en banca i energia, el seu creixent enfocament en un nombre reduït d'empreses i el paper clau de socis econòmics com el Regne Unit. En traçar les etapes de la internacionalització del mercat de valors, l'article revela el paper essencial del capital estranger a la dècada de 1960 i des de la integració europea en endavant.

PARAULES CLAU: Inversió estrangera, borsa de valors, globalització, Espanya

CODIS JEL: N24, F21, G15, G11

La inversión extranjera y el desarrollo de la bolsa de valores en España (1961-2007)

RESUMEN

Este artículo reconstruye las dinámicas de la inversión extranjera en la bolsa española entre 1961 y 2007, explorando esta dimensión menos conocida de la globalización financiera y la modernización del mercado en España. Mediante la construcción de una base de datos novedosa, analiza las tendencias de inversión por sectores, empresas, países de origen y tipos de inversores, ofreciendo una visión detallada de la evolución del capital extranjero durante la reintegración de España en la economía global. Los resultados destacan la concentración de la inversión extranjera en banca y energía, su creciente enfoque en un número reducido de empresas y el papel clave de socios económicos como el Reino Unido. Al trazar las etapas de la internacionalización del mercado de valores, el artículo revela el papel esencial del capital extranjero durante los años 1960 y desde la integración europea en adelante.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Inversión extranjera, bolsa de valores, globalización, España

CÓDIGOS JEL: N24, F21, G15, G11